

SOFTWARE AND INFORMATION SOLUTIONS ENGINEERING WITH HIGH AND LOW REGULATION: A COMPARISON OF FINTECH AND THE HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY

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Abstract. This article examines how different levels of regulation shape information solutions engineering in different sectors, using a PESTLE-based comparison of the USA, China, Russia and Slovenia. Two modes of regulation are identified. The first is high in vertical sectors such as civil engineering, agriculture, logistics, MedTech, and the military industry, which have similarities and where the research results can potentially be mutually transferable. The second mode is low, the most notable representative of which is the hospitality industry. The FinTech - hospitality industry IT comparison highlights a sharp contrast. While FinTech follows a compliance-first model, hospitality IT is more market-driven, with lighter sector-specific regulation. The study shows that regulatory intensity strongly affects management and implementation across different national environments and reveals similarities and differences between industries.

Keywords: software engineering, information solutions engineering, software and information solutions engineering, regulatory intensity, FinTech, hospitality industry, PESTLE-analysis, compliance-oriented development, market-driven development

1. Introduction

Recently, software engineering and information solutions engineering have been mentioned together often. The reason can be that a number of important and recognized recent studies show that they have many similarities in their historical development, research topics, design problems, and practical challenges today [1; 2]. These works also support the idea that software development and the broader development of information solutions should be studied together much closer as a software and information solutions engineering.

Numerous studies in the field of software and information solutions engineering and financial technology (FinTech) indicate the existence of economic and management differences between software and information solutions engineering in general and in the finance sector [3; 4; 5], which belongs to the service industries, as well as in many other sectors, including civil engineering IT [6; 7], agricultural IT [8], logistics IT [9], medical technology (MedTech) [10], military IT [11], and hospitality industry IT [12; 13].

Among the others, the latter is the most notable representative of low-regulated service industries based on the same pre-research [14]. Therefore, it was selected for analysis and comparison with the FinTech field.

The differences mentioned at the beginning cover such areas as management approaches, methods and methodologies, economic principles, and legal frameworks related to the development, implementation, and use of IT solutions in industries [15; 16; 17; 18]. Highly regulated industries are inclined to use and maintain traditional management methodologies and approaches, such as Waterfall, and economic principles. Others, usually less regulated, tend to adapt and use more modern, open, adaptive and efficient management approaches, such as agile [15; 19], and economic principles, such as the principles of open-source software [17] or platform economics [14].

Here regulatory intensity is an important factor shaping software and information solutions engineering across industries. Highly regulated sectors, such as FinTech and civil engineering IT, which were already mentioned and selected for the analysis, require compliance-oriented, documented, risk-aware, and often more formalized development. The reason for this is that regulation affects governance, cybersecurity, interoperability, and project management from the beginning [3; 5; 7]. In contrast, less regulated sectors, such as hospitality IT, are shaped more by customer expectations, operational efficiency, service quality, and market competition. This allows greater flexibility, faster experimentation, and more agile innovation. At the same time privacy, payment security and cybersecurity still remain relevant constraints [12; 13; 20; 21].

The comparison between FinTech and hospitality industry IT is current and important. It shows the contrast between a highly regulated digital sector and a more market-driven one, which was already mentioned and described. This makes the topic relevant for analysing, particularly in terms, how lower regulation allows greater flexibility, faster experimentation and more agile IT development, while still requiring attention to privacy, payment security and cybersecurity.

The object of this research is the comparison between highly regulated FinTech IT and less regulated hospitality industry IT, focusing on how different regulatory intensity affects software and information solutions engineering practices, flexibility, innovations, management, and market responsiveness.

The subject of this research is the impact of different regulatory intensity on software and information solutions engineering practices in FinTech and hospitality industry IT. Particularly in relation to compliance, agility, innovation, market orientation, user-centred development, and operational flexibility.

2. Methodology

For the purpose of the research, it was decided to conduct an analysis of individual vertical economic sectors using the PESTLE model. The analysis was planned as done for individual representative countries, with a subsequent comparison of the results across these countries and selected sectors.

PESTLE is a strategic analysis model used to examine the macro-environmental forces that shape organizational decisions, particularly Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal, and Environmental conditions [22; 23]. It is primarily used to identify opportunities and threats in the external environment so that managers can align strategy with broader contextual changes. At the same time, it is important that scholars also note that the model is often criticized for being broad, largely qualita-

tive, and sometimes insufficiently precise unless combined with other analytical tools [22; 23].

For the purpose of the research, countries currently representing the most politically, economically and technologically developed powers in the world were selected: the United States of America (USA), China, Russia and European Union (EU) [24; 25; 26; 27; 28; 29; 30]. In the latter, Slovenia was chosen as the representative country (Table 1). The main reasons for selecting an individual country for the purpose of analysis are the disunity of the EU and the high degree of independence of its members in the areas of politics and economics.

The countries were selected according to three main criteria. The first is global political and economic significance. The second is technological development, The third is diversity of regulatory models. The USA and China were chosen because they represent two of the most influential global economic and technological powers, but with different market and state-regulation traditions. Russia was included because it provides an example of a large, strategically important, and more sovereignty-oriented regulatory environment. Also, it still remains a significant world power, especially in a political sense. The EU is a major regulatory and economic actor, while its member states still preserve considerable independence in political, economic, and implementation practices. Together, selected countries allow comparison across market-driven, state-directed, sovereignty-focused, and EU-shaped approaches to software and information solutions engineering regulation.

Table 1

Slovenia - EU Comparison

Indicator	Slovenia	EU	References
GDP per capita (PPS) (2020-2024 average)	89.2% of the EU average (+2 p.p.)	100% (+1.1 p.p.)	[31; 32]
Actual individual consumption per capita (2022-2024 average)	85% of the EU average in average	100%	[31; 32]
Employment rate (2020-2024 average)	72.1% (+1.2 p.p.)	69.4% (+1.9 p.p.)	[33]
Unemployment rate (2020-2024 average)	3.9% (-0.9 p.p.)	6.2% (-0.8 p.p.)	[33]
ICT specialists as % of employment (2020-2024 average)	4.18% (+0.4 p.p.)	4.64% (+0.7 p.p.)	[33]
Digital strategy measures	81 measures	-	[33; 34]
Digital strategy budget	EUR 685 million (1.02% of GDP)	-	[33; 34]

The objectives of the research were:

1. To analyze and determine the differences between individual sectors regarding the level of regulation.
2. If there are, how do these affect software and information solutions engineering for these sectors?
3. If there are, compare the vertical sectors with each other.
4. Based on the potential comparative analysis, to prepare findings and recommendations for experts, managers, and scientists in the field for their work and research.

The research questions were defined as:

1. Are there differences between selected sectors regarding the level of regulation?
2. If the differences are present, what are those differences between selected sectors regarding the level of regulation?
3. If the differences are present, how do they affect software and information solutions engineering in the areas selected for research?
4. If the differences are present, compare them among themselves across different vertical sectors.
5. If the differences are present, compare their influence among themselves across different vertical sectors.

In general, the research was conducted by defining research mentioned questions, selecting databases and keywords based on these questions and selected countries, filtering, screening titles, abstracts and full texts, and then extracting and analysing relevant data. Individual groups or clusters were formed by comparing recurring themes, methods, sectors, technologies, variables and theoretical perspectives. Then similar studies were grouped together to support structured analysis and comparison.

More specifically the literature review was conducted by selecting scientific and professional sources based on their relevance, popularity, and recognition in academic databases such as Google Scholar, Scopus, and Web of Science (WoS), as the largest and most recognized international and interdisciplinary ones. The recognition assessment was based on the number of citations. The sources were then grouped into sectoral clusters, which were FinTech and hospitality industry IT, to compare how different levels of regulation affect software and information solutions engineering across industries and countries.

3. Research

3.1. Theoretical Basis

The topic of high and low regulated industries comes from studies on FinTech regulation and compliance-first software and information solutions engineering and from hospitality IT research focused on digitalisation, smart hotels, cloud systems, AI, service innovation, and customer experience. Scientific sources show that FinTech as was mentioned, has been researched as a highly regulated IT field, while hospitality IT, again as was mentioned, is usually studied as a more flexible, market-driven sector. This makes their comparison useful for understanding how regulation changes software and information solutions engineering methods, innovation speed, and management approaches.

The theoretical basis of this topic combines studies on FinTech regulation and compliance-oriented software and information solutions engineering with research on hospitality digitalisation, IT strategy, smart hotels, and service innovation. The most significant sources include Jinasena et al. [35], Munteanu and Dragos [5], and Letelay et al. [36] for FinTech, and Wynn and Jones [12], Wynn and Lam [13], Qiu et al. [20], Wang and Fu [37], and Yolcu et al. [38] for hospitality IT. Together, these sources show that FinTech is theoretically grounded in compliance, security, and risk control, while hospitality IT is grounded more in customer experience, agility, digital service quality, and market-driven innovation.

3.2. FinTech

FinTech refers to the use of digital technologies in financial services, including payments, banking infrastructure, consumer finance, digital assets, open banking, cybersecurity, and regulatory technology. In the article, FinTech can be presented as a highly regulated sector where software and information solutions engineering is shaped by financial stability, consumer protection, payment security, data governance, and cybersecurity requirements. Therefore, FinTech innovation usually follows a compliance-first logic, requiring strong governance, documentation, resilience, and risk-aware development from the earliest stages of IT engineering [3; 5; 36].

The breakdown of the entire analysis for FinTech is presented in Table 2.

Table 2

Breakdown of PESTLE Analysis for FinTech

PESTLE factor	USA	China	Russia	Slovenia (EU)
Political	Active but fragmented state involvement; federal oversight is increasing for large non-bank payment apps and personal financial data rights [39; 40; 41].	Highly state-directed, with financial and cyberspace regulators steering digital finance toward stability, data security, and policy alignment [42; 43; 44; 45].	Strongly regulated and sovereignty-focused, with the Bank of Russia prioritizing domestic payment infrastructure, technological sovereignty, and security [46; 47].	EU-shaped and institutionally coordinated through digital-transformation policy, the Digital Decade roadmap, and the Bank of Slovenia innovation contact point [48; 49].
Economic	Large and deep market, but investment has shifted toward profitable B2B infrastructure, payments, and compliance-oriented firms [50; 51].	Very large transaction scale and consumer usage, with 86 percent mobile-payment penetration and 185.147 billion mobile-payment transactions in 2023 [52; 53].	Large domestic digital-payments base, but more closed and nationally controlled. Cashless payments reached 88 percent of retail turnover and Fast Payments System (SBP) processed 13.4 billion transactions in 2024 [54; 55].	Small but EU-connected market suited to infrastructure-led models, although growth is limited by digital-transformation and SME digital-maturity bottlenecks [31; 56].

Social	Consumers increasingly expect faster, cheaper, more transparent, and portable digital financial services, while inclusion gaps remain [57; 58].	Very high acceptance of digital finance, but regional and demographic divides persist, especially among older and less digitally connected users [59; 60].	Users are familiar with domestic payment technologies such as QR payments, e-wallets, biometrics, Mir, and SBP, while fraud and security risks remain important concerns [55; 61].	Digital ambition is strong, but limited digital skills, SME readiness, trust, and security concerns constrain adoption [48; 62; 63].
Technological	Innovation-rich stack, with AI, cybersecurity, third-party dependencies, and layered controls becoming central engineering issues [64; 65].	Advanced payment architecture combined with e-CNY development and strict data-flow obligations [66; 67; 68].	Built around national rails and sovereign infrastructure, including SBP, Mir, the digital ruble, and DFAs, but constrained by cyberattacks and sanctions-related technology limits [69; 70; 71].	Technologically promising but ecosystem-sized, with payment rails, open-banking pathways, and possible digital-euro integration [48; 56].
Legal	Complex and multi-agency legal environment, especially for consumer protection, data rights, crypto-related risks, and digital payments [40; 41; 72].	Tight licensing and stringent data-security regime, including network-data and cross-border data-flow rules [44; 67; 68].	Highly restrictive and security-heavy, with DFA regulation and stricter personal-data localization, consent, and cross-border-transfer rules [70; 73; 74].	EU rulebook is decisive; ZInV-1, MiCA implementation, and DAC8/CARF reporting increase compliance burdens and create RegTech opportunities [75; 76].
Environmental	Indirect but growing relevance. Green-finance innovation is expanding, while AI/data-centre electricity demand creates sustainability pressure [77; 78].	Environmental policy is increasingly finance-linked, with studies connecting FinTech to greener capital allocation, carbon-efficiency, and lower emissions [79; 80].	Weaker but relevant driver: digital finance can support environmental financing and green investment, although sanctions and infrastructure limits constrain broader impact [71; 81].	Green transition creates indirect FinTech upside through sustainability-linked sovereign issuance and central-bank climate investing. Sustainability knowledge remains general rather than specific [17; 82; 83].

3.3. Hospitality Industry IT

Hospitality industry IT refers to the use of digital technologies in hotels, restaurants, tourism services, and accommodation management. This includes booking platforms, property management systems, mobile check-in, contactless services, AI-

based personalization, smart rooms, payment integration, and energy management tools. Hospitality IT can be presented as a comparatively low-regulated and market-driven sector, where software and information solutions engineering is shaped mainly by customer expectations, service quality, operational efficiency, labour shortages, personalization, and competitive pressure. Therefore, hospitality IT allows greater flexibility, faster experimentation, and more agile development than highly regulated sectors, while still requiring attention to privacy, cybersecurity, payment security, accessibility, and sustainability [12; 13; 20; 37; 38].

The breakdown of the analysis for hospitality industry IT is presented in Table 3.

Table 3

Breakdown of PESTLE Analysis for Hospitality Industry IT

PESTLE factor	USA	China	Russia	Slovenia (EU)
Political	Governance is more market-led than strategy-led, but FTC enforcement, ADA accessibility rules, PCI DSS, NIST guidance, and state privacy rules create practical IT governance requirements [84; 85; 86; 87; 88; 89].	Strongly state-led digitalisation, with smart tourism policy promoting upgraded digital infrastructure, 5G, AI-enabled services, smarter platforms, and data-based monitoring [90; 91].	Tourism is governed through the national project “Tourism and Hospitality” to 2030 and supported by state digital-platform development such as Russia.travel/RussPass [92; 93].	Clear public strategy. Slovenian tourism and digital-transformation strategies place digitalisation, sustainability, and data-driven destination management at the centre of tourism policy [94; 95; 96].
Economic	Large and mature market where labor shortages, operating costs, and guest-demand changes strengthen the case for automation and self-service IT [97; 98; 99].	Massive demand scale, supported by billions of domestic trips and a very large hotel base. It is creating a large market for booking, payment, automation, and energy-management systems [100; 101].	Domestic tourism and investment support growth, while labor shortages and cost pressure increase demand for AI and productivity-enhancing systems [102; 103; 104].	Growing tourism and strong dependence on digital channels support IT adoption, but SME resource and capability constraints slow advanced technology uptake [105; 106; 107].
Social	Guests increasingly expect mobile check-in, digital keys, contactless service, personalization, and human-centered digital support [20; 108; 109].	Consumers are receptive to mobile-first and smart-hotel experiences, but expect reliability, personalization, and a balance between automation and human service [37; 110; 111].	Adoption is mixed. Digital services improve convenience. However, staff readiness, digital literacy, motivation, and preservation of the human factor remain important [112; 113].	Adoption is strongly manager dependent. AI uptake is shaped by attitudes, ownership structure, perceived opportunity, cost concerns, skills, and fear of losing human interaction [114; 115].

Technological	Cloud PMS/CRS, AI revenue management, unified guest-data platforms, smart rooms, and cybersecurity-by-design are key opportunities. However legacy fragmentation remains a barrier [38; 89; 116].	Rapid uptake of smart-hotel systems, super-app payments, AI service tools, IoT, robots, and mobile-payment integration [90; 117; 118; 119; 120].	Core themes include online booking, mobile apps, smart rooms, chatbots, AI systems, contactless services, and nationally controlled payment rails such as SBP [54; 112; 121].	Strong basic digital foundations but uneven maturity; advanced analytics and AI adoption remain limited by cost, skills, and organizational readiness [106; 114; 115].
Legal	Privacy and compliance are fragmented but significant because hotels must manage payment data, personal data, accessibility, and cybersecurity obligations [84; 85; 86; 87; 88].	Highly structured data-governance regime under the Cybersecurity Law, Data Security Law, PIPL, and Network Data Security Management Regulations [122; 123; 124].	Strict data-protection and localization environment affects booking, guest-data storage, and cloud hospitality systems [125; 126].	EU law dominates. GDPR and the EU AI Act make privacy, cybersecurity, AI governance, and vendor governance strategic concerns [127; 128].
Environmental	Sustainability is driven by utility costs, brand pressure, and eco-innovation; IoT HVAC optimization, energy analytics, and predictive maintenance are important IT opportunities [129; 130].	Digitalisation and sustainability increasingly converge through green hotel management, smart energy management, AI load forecasting, and building-monitoring systems [131; 132; 133].	Environmental opportunities focus on energy monitoring, smart building control, and digital support for green-hotel models, especially in regional tourism projects [134].	Strong green-digital linkage: national strategy promotes sustainable tourism, and ICT use can reduce energy/material consumption, but measurement remains weaker than implementation [96; 135].

As part of the analysis of the political aspect, Table 4 presents an additional, approximate calculation of the number of regulations in selected industries for each of the selected countries. For the USA, the calculation was based on Federal Register data. [136]. For China, the calculation was based on data from the Database of National Laws and Regulations [137]. For Russia, the approximate number of industry-related regulations was estimated through searches in official legal-act databases of the Ministry of Justice [138; 139]. Because Russia’s regulatory system includes not only laws and decrees but also registered executive acts, technical standards, and mandatory requirements, the results should be interpreted as approximate indicators of regulatory intensity rather than exact counts of regulations. For Slovenia, the calculation was based on data from the Legal Information System of the Republic of Slovenia (PisRS) [140].

Number of Regulations in the Analysed Industries

	FinTech	Hospitality Industry
USA	Up to 300	Up to 8
China	At least 38	Up to 10
Russia	At least 27	Up to 8
Slovenia (EU)	At least 36	Up to 8

4. Discussion

The comparison between FinTech and hospitality industry IT shows a sharp contrast in regulatory intensity and its influence on IT-engineering.

FinTech is clearly a high-regulation sector, where digital products are developed under strong legal, political, and technical constraints. IT solutions must address regulatory compliance from the start, especially in relation to financial supervision, payment systems, anti-fraud controls, personal-data rights, and cybersecurity. Innovation is therefore possible, but it is usually shaped by a “compliance-first” logic.

Hospitality IT, in contrast, is a much less regulated and more market-driven environment. Although the sector still faces important legal obligations in areas such as privacy, accessibility, payment security, and platform governance, it is generally influenced more by customer expectations, operational efficiency, labor shortages, personalization, and competitive pressure than by dense sector-specific regulation. This gives hospitality firms more freedom to experiment with cloud systems, contactless services, AI-based guest management, mobile tools, and self-service technologies. In comparison with FinTech, hospitality IT therefore has greater room for flexibility, faster iteration, and user-centred innovation.

This contrast has important managerial implications. While FinTech often benefits from structured governance, strong documentation and risk-controlled development cycles, hospitality IT is better positioned to adopt agile, adaptive and service-oriented approaches that respond quickly to changing guest needs and market trends. At the same time, the comparison also shows that lower regulation does not eliminate constraints; instead, it shifts the emphasis from formal compliance to usability, integration, cost efficiency and digital maturity. Therefore, the main difference is not whether regulation exists, but how strongly it determines the logic of IT engineering. FinTech is shaped by regulation as a core design condition. Hospitality IT is shaped primarily by market responsiveness, with regulation functioning as a secondary boundary rather than the main organizing principle.

Notable and important here is comparison of two analysed countries: Slovenia and Russia, which reveals several important similarities. These two countries were selected for analysis due to the best similarity among the analysed countries in terms of their history, cultural background, and national economy. In FinTech, both countries treat digital finance as an area requiring strong legal oversight, secure infrastructure, and careful control of personal and transactional data, which means that IT development is shaped by regulation to a much greater extent than in less regulated sectors.

In hospitality IT, although regulation is lighter than in FinTech, Slovenia and Russia still share a common pattern: in both countries, digital transformation is supported by public strategies, while practical adoption depends heavily on organizational readiness, digital skills, and the ability of firms to integrate new tools into service delivery. This means that despite differences in scale and political context, both countries show that the success of IT engineering depends not only on regulation itself, but also on the capacity of organizations and users to operate within a digitally changing environment.

The general cross-country comparison also adds value. China and Russia generally show stronger state direction, the United States shows a more fragmented but still demanding environment, and Slovenia reflects EU-shaped regulation combined with the limits of a smaller market. At the same time, the study identifies a recurring weakness across sectors: sustainability is usually acknowledged, but often only in broad and not sufficiently operational terms. This suggests an important direction for future research - how sustainability requirements can be translated into concrete IT engineering practices alongside regulatory compliance and sectoral efficiency goals.

5. Conclusion

Concluding it can be surely stated that regulation operates in two main modes. The first is a high-regulation mode, typical of vertical sectors such as civil engineering, agriculture, logistics, MedTech, and the military industry. These sectors share certain similarities, making research findings potentially transferable between them. The second is a low-regulation mode, with the hospitality industry serving as its most prominent example.

The comparison between FinTech and hospitality industry IT highlights a much stronger contrast. FinTech clearly represents a high-regulation environment, where software and information solutions engineering is shaped by formal legal oversight and secure infrastructure requirements. Hospitality IT, in contrast, operates in a more market-driven and lightly regulated context, where technology decisions are influenced more by guest expectations, operational efficiency, labour shortages, and service quality than by sector-specific regulatory systems. Although privacy, payment security and accessibility remain relevant in hospitality, they do not dominate IT development to the same extent as in FinTech.

This contrast leads to an important conclusion, that the lower regulatory intensity of hospitality-IT allows greater space for agility, rapid experimentation and user-centered innovation, while FinTech must integrate innovation with compliance from the start. Therefore, the results show that software and information solutions engineering cannot be understood independently of its sectoral environment. Regulation not only changes technical requirements but also influences management style, development speed, and the balance between control and flexibility. In this sense, FinTech and hospitality IT represent two opposite poles that clearly demonstrate how regulatory intensity shapes modern software and information solutions engineering practice.

It is also important to note, that the analysed vertical markets in different countries, such as Russia and Slovenia, mentioned and compared in the discussion, have similarities that indicate that the findings determined during the research are not coinci-

dental. As already mentioned, all the countries selected for the analysis have different conditions. At the same time, the results between all of them are complimentary in many aspects. Therefore, it can be concluded that the findings of the research and the recommendations determined on its basis and presented below are certainly valid for the analyzed countries and sectors there and may be generally valid for other similar countries and sectors.

Based on the research findings, the following recommendations can be made:

1. Software and information solutions engineering practices should be aligned with the level of sectoral regulation.

2. Less regulated sectors such as hospitality IT should leverage their regulatory flexibility to adopt agile, customer-oriented, and innovation-driven approaches. At the same time, they should still ensure basic standards for privacy, cybersecurity, and payment security.

3. Highly regulated sectors like FinTech should prioritize compliance by design, strong governance, documentation, risk control, and structured or hybrid development methodologies.

4. Across all sectors and countries, digital skills, organizational readiness, interoperability, and standardization are critical success factors, so it is essential to develop them.

5. Sustainability requirements should be translated into concrete and measurable software and information solutions engineering practices rather than remain general policy goals.

Overall, this research is important because it demonstrates that differences in regulatory intensity fundamentally shape sector-specific models of software and information solutions engineering. Future research should therefore focus on expanding the comparison to additional industries to refine measurement of regulation across contexts. Also, they should focus on examining how sustainability and management methodologies and approaches can be operationalized more precisely within both highly and lightly regulated digital environments.

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ИНЖЕНЕРИЯ ПРОГРАММНОГО ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ И ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫХ РЕШЕНИЙ В УСЛОВИЯХ ВЫСОКОГО И НИЗКОГО РЕГУЛИРОВАНИЯ: СРАВНЕНИЕ ФИНТЕХ И ИНДУСТРИИ ГОСТИНИЧНОГО ДЕЛА

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Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается, как различные уровни регулирования влияют на разработку информационных решений в разных секторах, с использованием PESTLE-анализа США, Китая, России и Словении. Выделены два режима регулирования.

Первый - высокий в таких вертикальных секторах, как гражданское строительство, сельское хозяйство, логистика, медицинские технологии и военная промышленность, которые имеют сходства, и результаты исследований в которых потенциально могут быть взаимно переносимы. Второй режим - низкий, наиболее ярким представителем которого является индустрия гостиничного дела. Сравнение финтех и IT индустрии гостиничного дела выявляет резкий контраст. В то время как финтех следует модели, ориентированной на соблюдение нормативных требований, IT индустрии гостиничного дела в большей степени ориентирован на рынок, с более мягким отраслевым регулированием. Исследование показывает, что интенсивность регулирования сильно влияет на управление и внедрение в различных национальных средах и выявляет сходства и различия между отраслями.

Ключевые слова: разработка программного обеспечения, разработка информационных решений, разработка программного обеспечения и информационных решений, интенсивность регулирования, финтех, индустрия гостиничного дела, PESTLE-анализ, ориентированная на соблюдение нормативных требований разработка, ориентированная на рынок разработка